

Realization of the regenerative potential of alfalfa tissue cultures under conditions of increased sucrose content

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Four varieties of alfalfa characterized by different regeneration potential were involved in cell selection for drought tolerance after preliminary ranking. Drought was modeled by using elevated concentrations of sucrose in a solid nutrient medium. Normal regenerated plants were formed only for the Goyazan variety in the medium containing 45 g/l of sucrose and for the Leader variety in the medium containing 60 g/l of sucrose. The regenerants were planted in the soil, and after preliminary adaptation, they were grown under lighting conditions of 10-12 thousand lx. with watering once every 3-4 days. During the formation of the root system in some regenerants of the Goyazan variety in test tubes, agar was stained in pink and lilac colors, which indicates the synthesis of anthocyanins in the roots.

Keywords: *Alfalfa, in vitro culture, sucrose, stress modeling, plant regeneration, root, anthocyanin*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change and land desertification lead to a reduction in sown areas. The removal of arable land from crop rotation is serious damage to agriculture. This challenge has also arisen in Azerbaijan, where currently 36 administrative regions are in zones with a high risk of desertification (az.sputniknews.ru, 2019). In this regard, the use of a grass-field farming system is of great importance, since it not only maintains but also increases soil fertility. It is known that alfalfa plays a special role in such crop rotations, as it enriches the soil with nitrogen that is biologically available to plants and is a valuable fodder crop. Considering the climatic conditions prevailing in the country, it is desirable to use varieties capable of producing a high yield with a relatively low need for moisture. Currently, a combination of cellular and traditional breeding methods is used to meet this challenge. Cell selection methods make it possible to simulate stress conditions and choose selective concentrations of stressors at which cells neither die nor completely lose their ability to morphogenesis. The somaclonal forms that have arisen under such conditions are the material for obtaining plant varieties that are resistant to adverse environmental factors.

The aim of this study was to obtain regenerated

plants from alfalfa cell culture grown on nutrient media with a high content of sucrose, which lowers the water potential of the cultivation medium.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Seeds of 4 varieties of alfalfa (Aran, Goyazan, Yaz chichai, Leader) were used as the material for the study.

Aseptic seedlings were obtained from the seeds of these varieties on ½ of Hamburg medium (B₅) (Mezentsev, 1980). Explants isolated from seedlings were passaged on nutrient media with the addition of phytohormones that stimulate the formation of callus tissue. After reaching the required weight, the calli were divided into 3 parts and planted on B₅ nutrient medium with the addition of 30 g/l sucrose (control, variant 1), 45 g/l sucrose (variant 2), and 60 g/l sucrose (variant 3).

After 10 days of cultivation, the calli were transferred to a medium for induction of morphogenesis containing 0.2 mg/l of BAP. The obtained embryoids for germination were transferred to B₅ medium without phytohormones. The regenerants were planted in the soil and after 10 days of adaptation, they were grown in lighting

conditions of 10-12 thousand lx., with watering once every 3-4 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seeds of the alfalfa varieties used in the experiment were preliminarily assessed for germination under conditions of atmospheric pressure created by various concentrations of sucrose (Drozdov, Udovenko, 1988). 4 varieties were selected for introduction into in vitro culture after ranking carried out at atmospheric pressure of 14 atmospheres: Leader – not resistant, Aran – slightly resistant, Goyazan and Yaz chichiai – relatively resistant (Asadova, 2022). The varieties were also preliminarily evaluated by their ability to realize their regeneration potential in vitro (Asadova, 2021). According to the results of this experiment, the Leader and Aran varieties were characterized by rather high regenerative potential and under standard conditions (Mezentsev, 1980) gave normal viable regenerated plants. In varieties Goyazan and Yaz chichiai, numerous morphogenesis was observed, which did not lead to the formation of normal regenerated plants.

The mentioned varieties were introduced into in vitro culture. Calluses were obtained according to the method (Mezentsev, 1980). After obtaining a sufficient mass, callus tissues were divided into 3 parts and planted on nutrient media containing 30 g/l (control), 45 g/l, and 60 g/l of sucrose. Morphogenesis was induced in calluses after 10 days of cultivation, i.e., in order to obtain somaclonal forms we used the method of single-stage selection. The single-stage selection is often used in in vitro technologies. There is evidence of obtaining callus cultures and plant forms resistant to osmotic stress using single-stage breeding (Tuchin and Dyachuk, 1994; Yegorova, 2013; Bugara and Yunusova, 2016). Certainly, not all plants demonstrate the required result, it largely depends on the species and even varietal affiliation of the plant. The varieties of alfalfa studied by us also demonstrated diverse results.

Observations revealed that numerous morphogenetic foci appeared in the calluses of varieties Aran and Yaz chichiai on media containing 45 g/l and 60 g/l sucrose, but the process of morphogenesis did not develop further. Thus, a decrease in the water potential due to an increase in the concentration of sucrose in the cultivation medium completely suppressed the realization of the morphogenetic potential in the Aran variety, which regenerated well in the control. The decrease in water potential had neither a positive nor a negative effect on the morphogenic abilities of calluses of the Yaz chichiai variety.

It should be noted that an increase in the concentration of sucrose had a positive effect on the morphogenetic ability of cell cultures of the Goyazan variety. Under control conditions, structures appeared in morphogenic calluses, from which regenerated plants did not form, but in the variant with 45 g/l of sucrose, the regenerative potential of this variety was realized by almost 100%. Therefore, we can conclude that in order to realize the regenerative potential of an individual genotype in the cell tissue, it is necessary to create a certain osmotic pressure (Yarmanov, Nazorbayeva, 2017), and this indicator is closely related to the characteristics of the genotype. The results of the experiment revealed that the seeds of the Goyazan variety withstand the increased osmotic pressure in the growing medium to a greater extent compared to other varieties. This indicates a good sucking power of the cells. And this means that not only water is well absorbed, but also mineral elements are well dissolved in the cultivation medium. Probably, this feature of the Goyazan variety can explain the observed 100% regeneration in the callus culture. There is a lot of information that one of the main functions of sucrose and a number of simple sugars that accumulate during stress is the protection of protein-lipid components of cell membranes from denaturation during dehydration (Franko, Melo, 2000). Thus, it is shown that sucrose can replace water in the structure of phospholipids under stress conditions that cause cell dehydration (Caffery et al., 1988). Therefore, in addition to the fact that simple sugars are universal osmotic agents, they are used by plants as an energy and building material (Kolupaev and Trunova, 1992; Asadova, 2002).

The regenerants of the Goyazan variety had well-developed stem and root systems. As mentioned above, the Leader variety demonstrated the weakest result when ranking for osmotolerance, but had a good ability to regenerate under in vitro conditions. Several somaclonal forms without a root system were obtained from callus cultures of this variety (options 2 and 3). There is information about the effect of reducing the chemical potential of water in the culture medium of wheat cell tissues on the frequency of occurrence of somaclonal variants (Tuchin, 2000). The author has shown that in breeding for tolerance to the low chemical potential of water in the culture medium, it is possible to obtain regenerative plants with increased resistance to drought. Such plants retain the ability acquired by callus cells to stabilize the chemical potential of water in tissues and maintain biosynthetic activity under conditions of moisture deficiency (Tuchin, 2000). In somaclones of the Leader variety, the formation of the root system

was stimulated but a well-developed root appeared only in the regenerant formed on a medium with 60 g/l of sucrose (Asadova et al., 2022).

The regenerants of both varieties were planted in seed conditions. When young plants were watered 1 time in 3 days at a high level of illumination after adaptation to soil conditions, yellowing of the leaves was noted, but in general, no wilting was observed. Wilting has been noted when watering was suspended for more than 4 days. This irrigation regime led to irreversible wilting. Massive yellowing and falling of leaves began. Then the plants died. But after 7-8 days, green seedlings appeared, which gave rise to new plants (Fig. 1). Thus, it is possible to assume that the root system of the regenerants tolerated the lack of irrigation quite favorably. The formation of a strong root system is essential for the life of the

plant, especially in drought conditions. Irreversible wilting of the stem part of the plant is possibly associated with a high level of illumination, which adversely affected the process of photosynthesis.

It should be noted that all regenerated plants were grown on nutrient media supplemented with 30 g/l of sucrose. At the same time, in test tubes with regenerated plants of the Goyazan variety, the agar turned pink and then lilac (Fig. 2) as the roots grew, which indicates the presence of anthocyanins in the medium.

The synthesis of anthocyanins indicates a high content of sugars in the root system. It was shown that the exogenous introduction of carbohydrates at high light intensity stimulated the accumulation of anthocyanins in the roots of corn and barley (Maslennikov, 2003).

Fig. 1. Seedlings on the roots of regenerated plants after their complete wilting:
a – Leader variety; b – Goyazan variety

Fig. 2. Coloring of the root system of the Goyazan variety's regenerated plants:
a – light pink; b – light lilac; c – lilac

Our results are supported by the author's conclusion since this experiment was also carried out under conditions of high light intensity and using nutrient media with different concentrations of sucrose. Despite the fact that sucrose in the composition of the nutrient medium leads to a decrease in its water potential, some authors argue that exogenously introduced fructose and sucrose, and to a lesser extent glucose, have a protective effect on plants (Jacomini, 1988; Kolupaev and Trunova, 1992; Kolupaev and Karpets, 2010; Takahashi, 2020) - protect thylakoid membranes (Asada, 1999); participate in the regulation of the formation of reactive oxygen species and their neutralization (Couee et al., 2006; Deryabin et al., 2007); play the role of signaling molecules associated with the plant hormonal system, affect the expression of genes that provide a protective effect under stress conditions (Pego et al., 2000; Rolland F., Sheen, 2005; Liu et al., 2015). At the same time, it is noted that mannitol and sorbitol do not demonstrate protective properties.

Based on the foregoing, it can be stated that as a result of a single-stage selection based on a decrease in the water potential of the environment, it is possible to create conditions for the realization of the regeneration potential of a non-regenerating variety; under selective conditions, obtain somaclonal forms for a variety that is unstable to osmotic pressure, but has a high regeneration potential; use forms synthesizing anthocyanins in further breeding in order to obtain secondary metabolites from cell cultures and fodder plants with pharmacological properties.

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Yonca hüceyrə kulturasında quraqlığın modelləşdirilməsi üçün saxarozanın müxtəlif qatılıqlarının istifadəsi

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İlkin sıralamadan sonra müxtəlif regenerasiya potensialı ilə səciyyələnən 4 yonca sortu *in vitro* quraqlığa davamlılıq seleksiyasına cəlb edilmişdir. Quraqlıq bərk qidalı mühitdə yüksək saxaroza qatılıqları vasitəsilə modelləşdirilmişdir. Normal regenerant bitkiləri yalnız Göyəzən sortu üçün 45 q/l saxaroza, Lider sortu üçün isə - 60 q/l saxaroza əlavə edilmiş mühitdə əmələ gəlmişdir. Regenerantlar torpağa əkilmiş və ilkin adaptasiyadan sonra 10-12 min lüks işıqlandırma şəraitində yetişdirilmişdir. Bitkilərin suvarması 3-4 gündən bir dəfə aparılmışdır. Göyəzən sortunun bəzi regenerantlarının kök sisteminin formalaşması zamanı aqarın çəhrayı və yasəmən rənginə boyanması qeydə alınmışdır, bu da köklərdə antosiyanın sintezinin gedişi haqqında xəbər verir.

Açar sözlər: Yonca, *in vitro* kultura, saxaroza, stress modelləşdirmə, bitki regenerasiyası, kök, antosianin